

Electronic Supplementary Information

Synthesis and Chelation Study of a Fluoroionophore and a Glycopeptide based on an Aza Crown Iminosugar Structure

Alexandra Bordes,^a Ana Poveda,^b Nathalie Fontelle,^a Ana Ardá,^b Jérôme Guillard,^a Yi Bin Ruan,^c Jérôme Marrot,^d Shuki Imaeda,^e Atsushi Kato,^e Jérôme Désiré,^a Juan Xie,^{c*} Jesús Jiménez-Barbero,^{b,f,g*} Yves Blériot^{a*}

^a Université de Poitiers, IC2MP, UMR CNRS 7285, Equipe "Synthèse Organique", Groupe Glycochimie, 4 rue Michel Brunet, 86073 Poitiers cedex 9, France

^b CICbioGUNE, Parque Tecnológico de Bizkaia, Derio-Bizkaia 48160, Spain

^c Université Paris-Saclay, ENS Paris-Saclay, CNRS, Photophysique et Photochimie Supra- et Macromoléculaires (PPSM), 4 avenue des sciences, 91190 Gif-sur-Yvette, France

^d Institut Lavoisier de Versailles, UMR-CNRS 8180, Université de Versailles, 45 avenue des États-Unis, 78035 Versailles Cedex, France

^e Department of Hospital Pharmacy, University of Toyama, 2630 Sugitani, Toyama 930-0194, Japan

^f IKERBASQUE, Basque Foundation for Science, 48009 Bilbao, Spain

^g Dept. Organic Chemistry II, Faculty of Science and Technology, University of the Basque Country, 48940 Leioa, Spain

General methods	p 2
Synthesis - Experimental procedures	p 3
NMR experimental details for ISAC 8	p 9
Table 1: NMR data for ISAC 8	p 9
Figure 1: ¹ H- ¹³ C HSQC experiment for 8	p 10
Copies of ¹ H and ¹³ C NMR spectra for new compounds	p 11
Crystallographic data for ISAC 9	p 21
Figure 2: Absorption and emission spectra of ISAC 9	p 22
Table 2: Glycosidases inhibition of ISAC 6 and 8	p 23

General Methods

All starting materials, reagents and anhydrous solvents were used as received without further purification from commercial suppliers. Air and H₂O sensitive reactions were performed in oven dried glassware and under Ar atmosphere. Moisture sensitive reagents were introduced via a dry syringe. Petroleum ether (PE) refers to the 40–60 °C boiling fractions. Reactions were monitored by thin-layer chromatography (TLC) using silica gel 60 F₂₅₄ 0.25 mm pre-coated aluminum foil plates, visualized by using UV₂₅₄ and/or phosphomolybdic acid stain [3 g 12MoO₃·H₃PO₄·xH₂O in 100 mL EtOH] followed by heating with a heat gun. Flash columns chromatography were performed using Macherey-Nagel silica gel 60 (15–40 μm).

NMR experiments for the synthesized compounds were recorded with a Bruker Avance 400 spectrometer at 400 MHz for ¹H nuclei and at 100 MHz for ¹³C nuclei. The chemical shifts are expressed in part per million (ppm) relative to TMS (δ = 0 ppm) and the coupling constant *J* in Hertz (Hz). NMR multiplicities are reported using the following abbreviations: br = broad, s = singlet, d = doublet, t = triplet, q = quadruplet, m = multiplet. For more detailed ISAC NMR studies, spectra were acquired on either Bruker DRX-500, Bruker AVIII-600 equipped with TBI [¹H, ¹³C, X-broad band] or TXI [¹H, ¹³C, ¹⁵N] probeheads, or Bruker AVIII-800 equipped with a Cryo TCI probehead. All data were acquired at 298 K, unless other temperature is specified. ¹H chemical shifts were internally referenced to the methyl singlet of TSP (3-trimethylsilylpropionate-*d*4) at 0 ppm; ¹³C chemical shifts were referenced externally also using TSP. All NMR experiments were performed in Na₂CO₃/NaHCO₃ buffer solution at pH=11, in 10% D₂O/90% H₂O or net D₂O. 1D ¹H NMR data were acquired over a ¹H width of 10–12 ppm into 32K data points. The water resonance was suppressed by presaturation using 1D-noesy pulse sequence provided by Bruker. 2D ¹H-¹³C HSQC NMR data were acquired over a ¹H frequency width of 10 ppm and a ¹³C width of 60–80 ppm centered at 50 ppm. Data were acquired with 16–96 transients into 2–4K complex data points for each of 256–512 *t*₁ increments.

HRMS were recorded on a Bruker micrOTOF spectrometer.

Optical rotations were measured using an Anton Paar MCP100 Polarimeter.

Absorption spectra were recorded on a Uvikon-940 KON-TRON spectrophotometer and corrected emission spectra were performed on a Jobin-Yvon Spex Fluorolog 1681 spectrofluorometer (1 cm quartz cell was used). The tested metal salts included Cu(NO₃)₂, AgNO₃, Zn(ClO₄)₂, and Hg(ClO₄)₂.

HPLC was carried out on a Water alliance system equipped with a UV/Visible variable wavelength detector and with a reverse-phase column chromatography (C18, 150x4.6 mm, 5 μm, 120 Å) at 30°C and 1mL/min. Method 1 used a linear gradient composed of A (0.2% TFA in water) and B (CH₃CN) beginning with A/B = 95/5 v/v and reaching A/B = 0/100 v/v within 20 min. All chromatograms were recorded at 210 nm.

Structural models for ISAC **8** were calculated with the MacroModel application within the Maestro software (version 12.3). An initial structure was minimized using conjugate gradients with the OPAL3* force field. A maximum number of 5000 iterations were employed with the PRCG scheme, until the convergence energy threshold was 0.05. The minimized structure was submitted to a conformational search protocol, using a Monte Carlo torsional sampling method (MCMC) with automatic setup during the calculation, energy window of 50 kJ mol⁻¹, 1000 maximum number of steps, and 100 steps per torsion of the bond to be rotated.

Synthesis - Experimental procedures

2-((2S,3S,4R,5R,6S)-6-(azidomethyl)-1-benzyl-3,4,5-tris(benzyloxy)piperidin-2-yl)acetic acid (**11**).

To a solution of compound **10** (850 mg, 1.44 mmol) in a mixture THF/*t*BuOH (1/1.8 mL) were added 2-methyl-2-butene (C=2.0 M in THF, 1.44 mL, 2.88 mmol, 2 eq) and a solution of sodium chlorite (195 mg, 2.16 mmol, 1.5 eq) and sodium phosphate monobasic (518 mg, 4.32 mmol, 3 eq) in H₂O (4 mL). The reaction mixture was stirred for 3h under Argon at room temperature (monitored by TLC, PE/EtOAc: 8/2). The crude was washed with H₂O (3x50 mL) and extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3x50 mL). The organic layers were dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated in vacuo. The residue was purified by flash chromatography (PE/EtOAc: 6/4) to give compound **11** (838 mg, 96%) as a colorless oil. R_f = 0.68 (PE/EtOAc: 7/3); [α]_D²⁰ = - 40.8 (c 0.9, CHCl₃); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃): δ(ppm) = 7.30-7.29 (m, 20H, CHAr), 4.82-4.70 (m, 3H, OCH₂Ph), 4.61 (t, 2H, J = 12.0 Hz, OCH₂Ph), 4.49 (d, 1H, J = 11.7 Hz, OCH₂Ph), 4.00 (d, 1H, J = 13.0 Hz, NCH₂Ph), 3.54 (m, 2H, NCH₂Ph, H-3), 3.50 (m, 5H, H-2, H-5, H-6, H-7, H-7'), 3.21 (m, 1H, H-4), 2.79-2.64 (m, 2H, CH₂CO); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CDCl₃): δ(ppm) = 173.3 (C=O), 137.9-136.6 (CAr), 129.5-128.0 (CHAr), 78.0-76.8 (OCH₂Ph), 75.7 (C-2), 73.0 (C-3), 54.1 (C-6), 54.0 (C-5), 53.6 (C-4), 51.3 (NCH₂Ph), 48.0 (C-7), 33.3 (CH₂CO); HRMS (ESI+) *m/z*: [M+H⁺] calcd. for C₃₆H₃₉N₄O₅: 607.2842, found: 607.2897.

2-((2S,3S,4R,5R,6S)-6-(aminomethyl)-1-benzyl-3,4,5-tris(benzyloxy)piperidin-2-yl)acetic acid (**12**).

To a solution of compound **11** (475 mg, 0.78 mmol) in a mixture THF/NH₄OH (6.0/0.6 mL) was added triphenylphosphine polymer bound (613 mg, 2.34 mmol, 3eq). The reaction mixture was stirred at 40°C overnight, then filtered through Celite and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The residue was diluted in Et₂O, filtered again and the filtrate concentrated. A fast filtration/purification on a silica chromatography column (EtOAc/MeOH: 9/1) afforded compound **12** (350 mg, 77%) as a yellow oil, which was directly used for the synthesis of **7**.

IminoSugar Aza Crown (**7**).

To a solution of compound **12** (350 mg, 0.603 mmol) in dry DMF (C=5.10⁻² M, 12 mL), under Argon at 0°C, were added BOP reagent (1.34 g, 3.02 mmol, 5.0 eq.) and DIPEA (526 μL, 3.02 mmol, 5.0 eq). The reaction mixture was stirred for 7h under Argon at 0°C (monitored by TLC, DCM/MeOH: 9/1). The mixture was washed with H₂O (2x50 mL), sat. NaCl (50 mL) and extracted with CH₂Cl₂. The organic layers were dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated in vacuo. The residue was purified by flash chromatography (DCM/MeOH: 9/1) to give compound **7** (576 mg, 65%, 2 steps from **11**) as a colorless oil. R_f = 0.16 (DCM/MeOH: 9/1); [α]_D²⁰ = + 35.7 (c 0.8, CHCl₃); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CD₃OD): δ(ppm) = 7.43-6.69 (m, 40H, CHAr), 5.00 (m, 2H, OCH₂Ph), 4.95 (m, 2H, OCH₂Ph), 4.90 (m, 2H, OCH₂Ph), 4.85 (m, 2H, OCH₂Ph), 4.80 (m, 1H, OCH₂Ph), 4.70 (m, 2H, OCH₂Ph), 4.45 (d, 1H, J = 13.0 Hz, NCH₂Ph), 4.40 (d, 1H, J = 13.1 Hz, NCH₂Ph), 4.35 (s, 1H, H-5'), 4.31 (dd, 1H, J = 9.7 Hz, J = 5.5 Hz, H-5), 4.10 (d, 1H, J = 8.4 Hz, H-4), 3.55-3.48 (m, 2H, H-6', H-

7a'), 3.45-3.38 (m, 7H, H-2', H-3, H-3', H-4', H-2, H-6, H-7a), 3.12 (m, 1H, H-9a'), 3.01 (m, 2H, H-7b, H-9b'), 2.90 (m, 3H, H-7b', H-8a', H-9a), 2.80 (m, 1H, H-8a), 2.71 (m, 1H, H-9b), 2.62 (m, 1H, H-8b'), 2.55 (m, 1H, H-8b); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, CD₃OD): δ(ppm) = 171.2, 170.9 (C=O), 140.5-137.5 (CAr), 128.8-127.4 (CHAR), 84.4 (C-4), 84.1 (C-4'), 79.4 (C-3), 78.6 (C-3'), 77.5 (C-5), 77.4-75.5 (OCH₂Ph), 73.2 (C-5'), 72.9-71.9 (OCH₂Ph), 57.6 (C-6), 56.5 (C-2), 55.0 (C-2'), 53.6 (NCH₂Ph), 51.5 (C-6'), 50.0 (NCH₂Ph), 39.7 (C-9), 35.9 (C-7'), 33.9 (C-9'), 33.5 (C-7), 26.1 (C-8), 26.0 (C-8'); HRMS (ESI+) *m/z*: [M+Na⁺] calcd. for C₇₂H₇₆NaN₄O₈: 1147.5686, found : 1147.5714.

IminoSugar Aza Crown (8).

To a solution of compound **7** (50 mg, 0.044 mmol) in a mixture DCE/H₂O (9:1, 5 mL) were added 12N HCl (14.7 μL, 0.176 mmol, 4 eq) and black Pd (100 mg). The reaction mixture was then stirred under H₂ atmosphere at 60°C for 15 h (monitored by TLC, DCM/MeOH: 8/2). Then the mixture was filtered three times through Celite and concentrated under reduced pressure to afford compound **8** (17 mg, 98%) as a colorless oil. R_f = 0.14 (DCM/MeOH/NH₄OH: 8/2/0.5); [α]_D²⁰ = + 19.7 (c 0.8, CHCl₃); ¹H NMR (400 MHz, D₂O): δ(ppm) = 3.79-3.70 (m, 4H, H-5, H-5', H-7a, H-7a'), 3.56-3.51 (m, 2H, H-4, H-4'), 3.15-3.07 (m, 4H, H-6, H-6', H-7b, H-7b'), 3.05-3.03 (m, 4H, H-2, H-2', H-3, H-3'), 2.78 (m, 2H, H-8a, H-8a'), 2.00 (m, 2H, H-8b, H-8b'); ¹³C NMR (100 MHz, D₂O): δ(ppm) = 173.5 (2x C=O), 75.7 (C-6, C-6'), 73.5 (C-5, C-5'), 72.0 (C-2, C-2'), 56.4 (C-3, C-3'), 51.5 (C-4, C-4'), 39.7 (C-8, C-8'), 34.2 (C-7, C-7'); HRMS (ESI+) *m/z*: [M+Na⁺] calcd. for C₁₆H₂₈NaN₄O₈: 427.1804, found: 427.1799.

IminoSugar Aza Crown (9). *N,N'*-[*N*-(1,5-dihydropyren-6-yl)acetamide]₂-[(2*S*,3*S*,4*R*,5*R*,6*S*)-1-benzyl-2-ethanamine-3,4,5-tri(benzyl-oxy)piperidine]₂.

To a solution of compound **5** (40 mg, 0.04 mmol) in acetonitrile (3 mL) were added 2-chloro-*N*-(1,5-dihydropyren-6-yl)acetamide¹ (27 mg, 0.09 mmol), TBAI (13 mg, 0.04 mmol), KI (30 mg, 0.18 mmol) and K₂CO₃ (20 mg, 0.14 mmol). The reaction mixture was stirred at 80 °C for 15 h, then after cooling down to rt, a solution of NaOH (1N, 5 mL) and DCM (5 mL) were added and the reaction mixture was stirred for 5 min. Water (10 mL) was added and the aqueous layer was extracted with DCM (2 x 10 mL). The organic layer was dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated under reduced pressure after filtration. The residue was purified by flash chromatography (DCM/MeOH/NH₄OH: 9/1/0.1) to give compound **21** (21 mg, 35%) as a colorless oil. R_f = 0.28 (DCM/MeOH/NH₄OH: 9/1/0.1); [α]_D²⁰ = + 91.2 (c 0.4, CHCl₃); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ (ppm) = 9.37 (m, 1H, NH), 9.11 (s, 1H, NH), 8.20-8.06 (m, 4H, CHAR), 8.05-7.91 (m, 12H, CHAR), 7.85 (d, 1H, *J* = 8.1 Hz, CHAR), 7.71 (d, 1H, *J* = 9.2 Hz, CHAR), 7.56 (q, 2H, *J* = 9.2 Hz, CHAR), 7.45-7.27 (m, 15H, CHAR), 7.26-7.03 (m, 20H, CHAR), 6.62 (t, 2H, *J* = 7.6 Hz, CHAR), 6.09 (t, 1H, *J* = 7.2 Hz, CHAR), 5.09 (d, 1H, *J* = 11.6 Hz, OCH₂Ph), 5.01 (d, 1H, *J* = 10.5 Hz, OCH₂Ph), 4.94 (d, 1H, *J* = 10.5 Hz, OCH₂Ph), 4.73 (d, 1H, *J* = 11.6 Hz, OCH₂Ph), 4.65 (d, 1H, *J* = 11.7 Hz, OCH₂Ph), 4.61-4.47 (m, 5H, OCH₂Ph), 4.43

¹ J. H. Kim, A.-R. Hwang, S.-K. Chang, *Tetrahedron Lett.* **2004**, 45, 7557-7561.

(d, 1H, $J = 11.9$ Hz, OCH₂Ph), 4.37-4.18 (m, 3H, OCH₂Ph, NCH₂), 4.08-3.93 (m, 3H, NCH₂, 2CH), 3.89-3.81 (m, 2H, 2CH), 3.80-3.63 (m, 3H, CH, 2CH₂), 3.59-3.47 (m, 3H, NCH₂, 2CH), 3.43-3.29 (m, 5H, 2NCH₂, 2CH, CH₂), 3.16 (d, 2H, $J = 16.9$ Hz, NCH₂, H-2), 3.10-3.04 (m, 1H, CH₂), 2.99-2.92 (m, 1H, CH₂), 2.87 (d, 1H, $J = 16.5$ Hz, NCH₂), 2.70-2.60 (m, 1H, CH₂), 2.38 (s, 2H, 2CH₂), 2.24-2.17 (m, 1H, CH₂), 2.00-1.91 (m, 1H, CH₂), 1.69 (s, 1H, CH₂), 1.44-1.29 (m, 1H, CH₂); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 100 MHz): δ (ppm) = 171.4, 170.3 (CO), 141.7, 139.4, 138.7, 138.6, 138.5, 138.3, 137.9 (C_{Ar}), 128.7, 128.6, 128.5, 128.4, 128.3, 128.2, 128.1, 128.0, 127.9, 127.7, 127.5, 127.4, 127.2, 127.0, 126.8, 126.2, 126.0, 125.4, 125.2, 125.1, 125.0, 124.7, 123.7, 123.0, 122.0, 121.2, 120.8 (CH_{Ar}), 85.0, 81.9, 78.4, 76.6 (CH), 76.1 (OCH₂Ph), 75.8 (CH), 75.7 (OCH₂Ph), 73.9 (CH), 73.0, 72.7, 72.0, 71.8 (OCH₂Ph), 62.5 (NCH₂), 60.4 (CH), 60.1 (NCH₂), 59.3, 57.0 (CH₂), 56.4 (2CH), 53.8, 53.2, 50.3 (NCH₂), 48.7 (CH), 47.9, 29.9, 28.2 (CH₂); HRMS (ESI) m/z : [M+H]⁺ Calcd. for C₁₀₈H₁₀₃N₆O₈: 1611.7830, found: 1611.7832.

Azepane (14).

A solution of trimethylphosphine (1M/toluene, 12.6 mL, 12.6 mmol, 3eq.) was added to a solution of azidolactol **13** (3.31 g, 6.96 mmol) in anhydrous THF (60 mL). The reaction mixture was stirred at 90°C for 2h, then cooled to rt and the solvents removed under reduced pressure to give the crude expected bicyclic hemiaminal. To a solution of this crude hemiaminal (3.00 g, 6.96 mmol) in dry THF (45 mL) was added dropwise at 0°C a solution of 3- magnesiumbromide-1-(trimethylsilyl)-1-propargyl (2.0 M in THF, 10.4 mL, 20.8 mmol, 3 eq). The reaction mixture was stirred at room temperature for 1h and diluted in EtOAc (100 mL). The crude was washed with Brine (200 mL). After separation, the aqueous layer was further extracted with EtOAc (2x50 mL). The combined organic extracts were dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue was then diluted in dry DMF (15 mL) and K₂CO₃ (2.89 g, 20.8 mmol, 3 eq.) and BnBr (1.25 mL, 10.4 mmol, 1.5 eq) were added at 0°C. The reaction mixture was stirred overnight under Argon at room temperature (monitored by TLC, PE/EtOAc: 8/2). The crude was washed with H₂O (2x50 mL) and extracted with EtOAc (3x50 mL). The organic layers were dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated in vacuo. The residue was purified by flash chromatography (PE/EtOAc: 9/1) to give **14** as a colorless oil (1.85 g, 49%, 3 steps). $R_f = 0.75$ (PE/EtOAc: 8/2); $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -18.4$ (C 0.7, CHCl₃); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ (ppm) = 7.35-7.19 (m, 20H, CH_{Ar}), 4.66-4.44 (m, 6H, OCH₂Ph), 3.97 (dd, $J = 6.9$ Hz, $J = 2.9$ Hz, 1H, H-4), 3.94 (m, 2H, H-6, NCH₂Ph), 3.82 (d, $J = 14.0$ Hz, 1H, NCH₂Ph), 3.72 (m, 2H, H-3, H-5), 3.38 (m, 2H, H-2, OH), 2.85 (m, 2H, H-7, H-7a), 2.55 (m, 2H, H-8, H-8a), 0.07 (s, 9H, (CH₃)₃Si); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 100 MHz): δ (ppm) = 139.6, 138.4, 138.2, 137.8 (C_{qAr}), 128.9-127.2 (CH_{Ar}), 105.7 (C-9), 86.8 (C-10), 85.7 (C-5), 83.3 (C-4), 79.5 (C-3), 73.2-72.2 (OCH₂Ph), 68.8 (C-6), 61.9 (C-2), 58.4 (NCH₂Ph), 52.7 (C-7), 18.0 (C-8), 0.1 ((CH₃)₃Si); HRMS (ESI) m/z : [M+H]⁺ Calcd. for C₃₈H₄₄N₅O₄: 634.3363; found: 634.3388.

Piperidine (15).

To a solution of compound **14** (2.00 g, 3.68 mmol) in CH₂Cl₂ (50 mL) were added at 0°C Et₃N (991 μ L, 7.36 mmol, 2 eq) and MsCl (445 μ L, 5.52 mmol, 1.5 eq). The reaction mixture was stirred for 1h under Argon at 0°C (monitored by TLC, PE/EtOAc: 9/1). The residue was diluted CH₂Cl₂, then few drops

of 1N HCl were added. The mixture was washed with H₂O and extracted with CH₂Cl₂. The organic layers were dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated in vacuo. The residue was purified by flash chromatography (PE/EtOAc: 95/5) to give **15** as a colorless oil (1.87 g, 78%). R_f = 0.92 (PE/EtOAc: 9/1); [α]_D²⁰ = -32.6 (C 0.5, CHCl₃); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ (ppm) = 7.48-7.26 (m, 20H, CHAr), 5.00-4.93 (dd, 2H, J = 18.2 Hz, J = 10.7 Hz, OCH₂Ph), 4.82-4.75 (dd, 2H, J = 18.1 Hz, J = 10.7 Hz, OCH₂Ph), 4.57-4.50 (qAB, J = 18.2 Hz, J = 6.7 Hz, 2H, OCH₂Ph), 4.05 (s, 2H, NCH₂Ph), 3.85 (m, 2H, H-7, H-7a), 3.69 (m, 3H, H-3, H-4, H-5), 3.39 (m, 1H, H-6), 3.03 (m, 1H, H-2), 2.92-2.75 (m, 2H, H-8, H-8a), 0.20 (s, 9H, (CH₃)₃Si); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 100 MHz): δ (ppm) = 139.4-138.0 (CqAr), 129.0-127.2 (CHAr), 103.5 (C-9), 87.7 (C-10), 83.4 (C-5), 81.8 (C-4), 80.5 (C-3), 79.2-68.1 (OCH₂Ph), 58.3 (C-6), 56.6 (C-2), 51.7 (NCH₂Ph), 39.6 (C-7), 20.8 (C-8), 0.2 ((CH₃)₃Si); HRMS (ESI) m/z: [M+H]⁺ Calcd. for C₄₀H₄₇NClO₃Si: 652.3021; found: 652.3008.

Piperidine (**16**) and Azepane (**17**).

A mixture of compound **15** (1.50 g, 2.30 mmol) and sodium

azide (300 mg, 4.61 mmol, 2.0 eq) in dry DMF (25 mL) was stirred at 80°C for 3h (monitored by TLC, PE/EtOAc: 95/5) then DMF was removed under high vacuum. The residue was diluted with EtOAc (50 mL) and washed successively with water (50 mL) and Brine (50 mL). The organic layer was dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated in vacuo. The residue was purified by flash chromatography (PE/EtOAc: 95/5) to afford the azepane **17** (333 mg, 22%) and the piperidine **16** (1.18 g, 78%) as colorless oils. Azepane **17**: R_f = 0.35 (PE/Et₂O: 95/5); [α]_D²⁰ = -54.0 (C 0.7, CHCl₃); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ (ppm) = 7.39-7.28 (m, 20H, CHAr), 4.74-4.46 (m, 6H, OCH₂Ph), 4.10-4.07 (m, 3H, H-4, H-5, NCH₂Ph), 3.86 (m, 2H, H-6, NCH₂Ph), 3.83 (dd, J = 8.2 Hz, J = 1.4 Hz, 1H, H-3), 3.72 (td, J = 9.0 Hz, J = 3.2 Hz, 1H, H-2), 3.16 (m, 1H, H-7), 2.99 (dd, J = 14.1 Hz, J = 4.7 Hz, 1H, H-7a), 2.76 (dd, J = 17.3 Hz, J = 3.4 Hz, 1H, H-8), 2.57 (dd, J = 17.2 Hz, J = 8.9 Hz, 1H, H-8a), 0.18 (s, 9H, (CH₃)₃Si); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 100 MHz): δ (ppm) = 140.1-137.8 (CqAr), 128.7-127.9 (CHAr), 106.3 (C-9), 86.6 (C-10), 84.4 (C-3), 80.6 (C-4), 78.5 (C-5), 77.5-72.6 (OCH₂Ph), 62.7 (C-2), 55.6 (C-6), 53.6 (CqNCH₂Ph), 50.2 (NCH₂Ph), 49.9 (C-7), 23.0 (C-8), 0.2 ((CH₃)₃Si); HRMS (ESI) m/z: [M+H]⁺ Calcd. for C₄₀H₄₇N₄O₃Si: 659.3427; found: 659.3412. Piperidine **16**: R_f = 0.31 (PE/Et₂O: 95/5); [α]_D²⁰ = 0.36 (C 0.9, CHCl₃); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ (ppm) = 7.38-7.27 (m, 20H, CHAr), 5.00-4.93 (dd, 2H, J = 18.1 Hz, J = 10.5 Hz, OCH₂Ph), 4.83-4.75 (dd, 2H, J = 18.2 Hz, J = 10.5 Hz, OCH₂Ph), 4.52 (qAB, J = 18.2 Hz, J = 6.8 Hz, 2H, OCH₂Ph), 3.98-3.93 (qAB, J = 19.2 Hz, J = 9.8 Hz, 2H, NCH₂Ph), 3.69 (m, 3H, H-3, H-4, H-5), 3.53-3.48 (m, 2H, H-7, H-7a), 3.15 (m, 1H, H-6), 3.06 (m, 1H, H-2), 2.92-2.76 (m, 2H, H-8, H-8a), 0.17 (s, 9H, (CH₃)₃Si); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 100 MHz): δ (ppm) = 139.3-137.9 (CqAr), 128.9-127.3 (CHAr), 103.5 (C-9), 87.8 (C-10), 84.0 (C-5), 80.4 (C-4), 78.3 (C-3), 77.5-72.8 (OCH₂Ph), 56.5 (C-2), 56.2 (C-6), 51.6 (NCH₂Ph), 46.3 (C-7), 20.8 (C-8), 0.2 ((CH₃)₃Si); HRMS (ESI) m/z: [M+H]⁺ Calcd. for C₄₀H₄₇N₄O₃Si: 659.3420; found : 659.3412.

Piperidine (18).

Experimental procedure 1: To a solution of compound **16** (1.15 g, 1.75 mmol) in MeOH (20 mL) was added K₂CO₃ (2.42 g, 17.5 mmol, 10 eq). The reaction mixture was stirred overnight under Argon at room temperature (monitored by TLC, PE/EtOAc: 9/1). The residue was diluted in CH₂Cl₂, then few drops of 1N HCl were added. The mixture was washed with H₂O and extracted with CH₂Cl₂. The organic layers were dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated in vacuo. The residue was purified by flash chromatography (PE/EtOAc: 7/3) to give **18** as a colorless oil (1.01 g, 98%).

Experimental procedure 2: To a solution of compound **19** (600 mg, 1.02 mmol) in a mixture 1,4-dioxane/H₂O (12 mL, 3/1) were added 2,6-lutidine (238 μL, 2.04 mmol, 2 eq), osmium tetroxide solution in *tert*butanol (2.5 %wt, 7 μL, 0.0204 mmol, 0.02 eq) and sodium periodate (873 mg, 4.08 mmol, 4.0 eq). The reaction was stirred for 1h under Argon at room temperature (monitored by TLC, EP/EtOAc: 9/1). The residue was diluted in 20 mL of CH₂Cl₂, and then few drops of HCl 1N were added. The mixture was washed with H₂O and extracted with CH₂Cl₂. The organic layers were dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated in vacuo. The residue was purified by flash chromatography (EP/EtOAc: 8/2) to give the expected aldehyde as a colorless oil (530 mg, 88%). To a solution of the aldehyde (450 mg, 0.765 mmol) in MeOH (5 mL) were added potassium carbonate (317 mg, 2.30 mmol, 3 eq) and dimethyl (1-diazo-2-oxopropyl)phosphonate solution (10% in ACN, 367 μL, 1.50 mmol, 2 eq). The reaction mixture was stirred for 2h under Argon at room temperature (monitored by TLC, PE/EtOAc: 8/2). The crude was washed with H₂O (3x50 mL) and extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3x50 mL). The organic layers were dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated in vacuo. The residue was purified by flash chromatography (PE/EtOAc: 7/3) to give **18** as a colorless oil (336 mg, 75%, 2 steps). R_f = 0.52 (PE/EtOAc: 8/2); [α]_D²⁰ = - 57.5 (C 0.9, CHCl₃); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ (ppm) = 7.29-7.10 (m, 20H, CHAr), 4.88 (t, 2H, J = 10.7 Hz, OCH₂Ph), 4.70 (dd, 2H, J = 14.8 Hz, J = 10.8 Hz, OCH₂Ph), 4.41 (qAB, J = 14.7 Hz, J = 3.1 Hz, 2H, OCH₂Ph), 3.86 (s, 2H, NCH₂Ph), 3.66-3.61 (m, 3H, H-3, H-4, H-5), 3.59-3.37 (m, 2H, H-7, H-7a), 3.08 (m, 1H, H-6), 3.06 (m, 1H, H-2), 2.98-2.61 (m, 2H, H-8, H-8a), 1.99 (t, J = 2.6 Hz, 1H, H-10); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 100 MHz): δ (ppm) = 139.1-137.9 (CqAr), 128.8-127.3 (CHAR), 83.8 (C-10), 80.9 (C-9), 80.3 (C-5), 78.4 (C-4), 75.7 (C-3), 75.6-71.4 (OCH₂Ph), 56.5 (C-2), 56.0 (C-6), 51.8 (NCH₂Ph), 46.3 (C-7), 19.5 (C-8); HRMS (ESI) m/z: [M+Na]⁺ Calcd. for C₃₇H₃₈N₄O₃Na: 609.2843; found : 609.2836.

Piperidine (20).

To a solution of compound **18** (1.00 g, 1.71 mmol) in CH₃CN/H₂O (5/1, 15 mL) was added ceric ammonium nitrate (3.75 g, 6.84 mmol, 4 eq). The reaction mixture was stirred for 15h under Argon at room temperature (monitored by TLC, PE/EtOAc: 7/3). The crude was washed with H₂O (3x50 mL)

and extracted with CH₂Cl₂ (3x50 mL). The organic layers were dried over MgSO₄ and concentrated in vacuo. The residue was purified by flash chromatography (PE/EtOAc: 5/5 then 3/7) to give compound **20** as a colorless oil (501 mg, 59%). R_f = 0.35 (PE/EtOAc: 6/4); [α]_D²⁰ = - 65.4 (C 0.9, CHCl₃); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃, 400 MHz): δ (ppm) = 7.35-7.28 (m, 15H, CHAr), 4.94-4.91 (dd, 2H, *J* = 14.8 Hz, *J* = 10.7 Hz, OCH₂Ph), 4.82-4.79 (d, 1H, *J* = 10.8 Hz, OCH₂Ph), 4.70-4.65 (m, 3H, OCH₂Ph), 3.75 (m, 1H H-2), 3.68-3.57 (m, 3H, H-3, H-4, H-5), 3.39-3.36 (m, 2H, H-7, H-7a), 2.91 (m, 1H, H-6), 2.60-2.58 (m, 1H, H-8), 2.50-2.48 (m, 1H, H-8a), 2.09 (t, *J* = 2.6 Hz, 1H, H-10); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 100 MHz): δ (ppm) = 138.7-138.1 (CqAr), 128.7-127.8 (CHAr), 83.1 (C-10), 82.1 (C-9), 80.8 (C-5), 80.5 (C-4), 77.5 (C-3), 77.4-71.5 (OCH₂Ph), 54.3 (C-2), 51.7 (C-6), 48.4 (C-7), 22.0 (C-8); HRMS (ESI) *m/z*: [M+Na]⁺ Calcd. for C₃₀H₃₃N₄O₃Na: 497.2532; found : 497.2503.

NMR experimental details for ISAC 8.

For ISAC structural study, NMR spectra were acquired on either Bruker DRX-500, Bruker AVIII-600 equipped with TBI [^1H , ^{13}C , X-broad band] or TXI [^1H , ^{13}C , ^{15}N] probeheads, or Bruker AVIII-800 equipped with a Cryo TCI probehead.

All data were acquired at 298 K, unless other temperature is specified. ^1H chemical shifts were internally referenced to the methyl singlet of TSP (3-trimethylsilylpropionate- d_4) at 0 ppm; ^{13}C chemical shifts were referenced externally also using TSP. All NMR experiments were performed in $\text{Na}_2\text{CO}_3/\text{NaHCO}_3$ buffer solution at pH=11, in 10% $\text{D}_2\text{O}/90\%$ H_2O or net D_2O .

1D ^1H NMR data were acquired over a ^1H width of 10-12 ppm into 32K data points. The water resonance was suppressed by presaturation using 1D-noesy pulse sequence provided by Bruker.

2D ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC NMR data were acquired over a ^1H frequency width of 10 ppm and a ^{13}C width of 60-80 ppm centered at 50 ppm. Data were acquired with 16-96 transients into 2-4K complex data points for each of 256-512 t_1 increments.

Table 1: NMR data for ISAC 8

δ (ppm) ^1H and δ ^{13}C data are extracted from HSQC experiments. Some relevant vicinal J couplings are also listed.

ISAC 8	δ ^1H (ppm)	δ ^{13}C (ppm)	J_{HH} (Hz)
H6'	2.0	40.1	13.2, 10.6
H6	2.8	39.8	13.3, 2.0
H5	3.1	51.5	10.1, 10.1, 2.0
H4	3.0	75.8	9.1, 9.1
H3	3.6	76.8	9.3, 9.3
H2	3.7	72.0	10.1, 5.8
H1	3.1	56.7	nd
H8'	3.1	34.4	nd
H8	3.8	34.4	13.7

Figure 1: ^1H - ^{13}C HSQC experiment for compound ISAC 8, with signal assignment

^1H NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) of compound **11**.

^{13}C NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 100 MHz) of compound **11**.

^1H NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) of compound 7.

^{13}C NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 100 MHz) of compound 7.

^1H NMR spectrum (D_2O , 400 MHz) of compound **8**.

^{13}C NMR spectrum (D_2O , 100 MHz) of compound **8**.

^1H NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) of compound **9**.

^{13}C NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 100 MHz) of compound **9**.

¹H NMR spectrum (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) of compound **14**.

¹³C NMR spectrum (CDCl₃, 100 MHz) of compound **14**.

¹H NMR spectrum (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) of compound **15**.

¹³C NMR spectrum (CDCl₃, 100 MHz) of compound **15**.

¹H NMR spectrum (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) of compound **16**.

¹³C NMR spectrum (CDCl₃, 100 MHz) of compound **16**.

¹H NMR spectrum (CDCl₃, 400 MHz) of compound **17**.

¹³C NMR spectrum (CDCl₃, 100 MHz) of compound **17**.

^1H NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) of compound **18**.

^{13}C NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 100 MHz) of compound **18**.

^1H NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 400 MHz) of compound **20**.

^{13}C NMR spectrum (CDCl_3 , 100 MHz) of compound **20**.

Crystallographic data for ISAC 9

CCDC 1451971

Summary of Data CCDC 1451971

Formula: C₁₀₈ H₁₀₂ N₆ O₈, C₃ H₆ O₁

Unit Cell Parameters: a 11.9176(10) b 30.094(2) c 12.9668(11) P21

Top and bottom left: full structure of ISAC 9; bottom right: aromatic rings have been removed.

Figure 2: Absorption and emission spectra of ISAC **9** ($c = 5.0 \mu\text{M}$) in different solvents. $\lambda_{\text{ex}} = 340 \text{ nm}$.

Table 2: Glycosidases inhibition of ISAC **6** and **8**

Concentration of iminosugars giving 50 % inhibition of various glycosidases		
	IC ₅₀ (μM)	
enzyme	6	8
α-glucosidase		
yeast	^a NI ^b (0%)	NI (0%)
rice	NI (19.6%)	NI (0%)
rat intestinal maltase	NI (0%)	NI (0%)
β-glucosidase		
almond	NI (0%)	NI (0%)
bovine liver	NI (15.6%)	NI (8.57%)
Rat intestinal cellobiase	NI (2.4%)	NI (0%)
α-galactosidase		
coffee beans	NI (6.5%)	NI (11.4%)
β-galactosidase		
bovine liver	NI (33.6%)	NI (6.5%)
α-mannosidase		
jack beans	NI (2.9%)	NI (2.2%)
β-mannosidase		
<i>helix pomatia</i>	NI (4.1%)	NI (0%)
α-L-fucosidase		
bovine kidney	NI (0%)	NI (0%)
α,α-trehalase		
porcine kidney	NI (2.6%)	NI (1.3%)
amyloglucosidase		
<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	NI (0%)	NI (0%)
<i>Rhizopus sp</i>	NI (0%)	NI (0%)
α-L-rhamnosidase		
<i>Penicillium decumbens</i>	NI (7.2%)	NI (4.2%)
β-glucuronidase		
<i>E. coli</i>	NI (0%)	NI (0%)
bovine liver	NI (0.54%)	NI (4.0%)

^a NI : No inhibition (less than 50% inhibition at 100 μM).

^b () : inhibition % at 100 μM